

MORPHING CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE USING ELECTROCHEMICAL ACTUATION

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ABSTRACT

Morphing structures have long been desired in the various industries to enable, for example, efficient fluid flow in different flow regimes. However, problems with mechanical complexity, weight, and large energy requirements have meant that morphing structures have only been sparingly utilised.

Current state of the art morphing technologies use systems of mechanical motors and hydraulics to create shape changes. These systems add parasitic weight, and are mechanically complex, adding to maintenance costs. Attempts have been made to use solid-state devices such as piezo-ceramics and shape memory alloys to create shape changes, however these devices rely on either extremely high voltages, or changes in atmospheric conditions in order to actuate. They also have comparatively poor mechanical properties. Here we present a concept of a solid-state electrochemically-actuated morphing structure manufactured from aerospace grade carbon fibre. The concept exploits expansions caused by lithium-ions intercalating into the carbon fibre microstructure. Both analytical and FE models are used to simulate a morphing three-layer laminate in a cantilever setup, and it is shown that relatively large deflections could be achieved, albeit at relatively low frequencies (in the range of mHz). An analysis of the likelihood of delamination occurring showed that there are no layups for which delamination is likely based on the estimated interlaminar strengths, and it is therefore unlikely that such a device would suffer from delamination in normal operational conditions. This concept paves the way for a new type of morphing structure that is mechanically simple, lightweight, and uses a low amount of energy to produce large shape changes without loss of mechanical integrity.

1 INTRODUCTION

In many industries there is a need for morphable structures that are capable of changing shape in a controllable way, while still being able to support a load. For example, in the renewable energy industry, it is advantageous for wind turbine blades to be able to trim their aerodynamic profile in order to stay within the efficiency and operational windows of their generators for a range of wind speeds. Current morphable structures most often rely on mechanical motors, hydraulics and solenoids to enable shape changes. These are often heavy, and mechanically complex, adding significant parasitic weight to the structure, as well as increasing the cost of maintenance. In order to avoid the mechanical complexity of having many moving parts, solid-state actuation for morphing has been used. These actuators include piezo-ceramics as well as shape-memory alloys (SMAs). Although these reduce mechanical complexity, they also have their own shortcomings. Piezo-ceramics require high voltages in order to provide actuation [1] while SMAs require a change in atmospheric conditions (temperature or pressure) in order to actuate [2].

More recently intercalation actuators have been suggested as a way of providing morphable structures. These work by inserting ions into the microstructure of a material causing it to expand. Actuation by ion intercalation has the distinct advantage that shape changes can be created in materials that have very good mechanical properties – such as carbon-based structures. Typically, intercalation-based actuators have a source of ions, a medium through which the ions travel (i.e. an electrolyte), as well as the intercalation material into which the ions are inserted. Ions are driven into the intercalation material by a small current, at low electrical potentials (typically $< 3\text{V}$).

Various ion intercalation actuators have previously been presented in literature, using different ions and different ion-intercalating materials. Massey et. al [3] used polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibre paper and intercalated them with hydrogen sulphate (HSO_4) producing transverse strains of up to 45%, albeit at elevated temperatures. This system, however, was non-structural, relying on a liquid sulphuric acid electrolyte (H_2SO_4) to transport the ions between the electrodes. Chin et. al [4] used off-the-shelf lithium (Li)-ion batteries and measured strains in the range of 1-3% when they were compressed and subsequently charged/discharged. Again, these actuators cannot be considered to be strictly structural since the majority of the structural properties arise from the casing in which the active battery materials are contained. Koyama et al. [5] manufactured a micro-actuator from graphite and showed that under compression it was possible to produce strains of $\approx 7\%$, although actuation strain rates were slow at more than 20 hours per cycle. They further showed a graphite-Li Cobalt Oxide (LiCoO_2) laminated macro-actuator that demonstrated a considerably higher strain rate (2.5 minutes/cycle), albeit with a lower strain of around 1%. Zhang & Grant [6] created a micro-actuator made from textured LiCoO_2 which achieved an actuation strain around 1.2%. Here again, the actuator cannot be considered to be structural since a liquid electrolyte needs to be used in order to transfer ions between the two electrodes.

Jacques et al. [7] showed that when Li-ions were intercalated into PAN-based carbon fibres, the fibres expanded along their fibre direction by as much as 1%. This expansion was shown to be largely reversible, with a small permanent expansion resulting from Li-ions becoming permanently trapped in the microstructure on the first charge cycle. Despite the relatively small expansion it was found that a large amount of mechanical work could be recovered from the expansion due to the high stiffness of the carbon fibres.

It is proposed here that it should be possible to exploit this expansion in a morphing structure. By combining two layers of carbon fibre and electrically insulating them from one another using a glass fibre separator layer, it should be possible to then embed the entire setup in an ionically conductive solid battery electrolyte (SBE) matrix, such as the ones presented in Ihrner et al. [8]. A schematic of such a laminate is shown in Figure 1. By exchanging ions from one electrode to the other by the application of a small current it should be possible to expand one electrode while the opposite electrode contracts. By altering the fibre directions of the layers it should be possible to produce a range of bending and twisting motions in the laminate.

Figure 1: 3-layer conceptual actuator device consisting of two active layers of carbon fibre, separated by a layer of glass fibre and embedded in an SBE matrix. Lithium (Li)-ions are transferred from one carbon fibre layer to the other causing the laminated structure to morph.

In this paper just such an actuator is modelled analytically using the methodology described by Dionisi et al. [9] and compared with an FE model of the same setup. The analytical model is based on classical lamination plate theory (CLPT) and uses a thermal expansion analogy to model the intercalation expansion caused by Li-ion intercalation. This is done using linearised experimental data from Jacques et al. [7], and uses this to form an intercalation expansion coefficient (analogous to a coefficient of thermal expansion) that designates the expansion of the carbon fibres at different electrochemical capacities (analogous to different temperatures).

Different layups are tested, with the fibre directions of one of the carbon fibre layers being rotated to produce a different mode of morphing. Results for maximum laminate deflection are given for different capacities, as well as mode shapes. An analysis of the interlaminar stresses is given to help predict the likelihood of delamination caused by the intercalation expansion.

It is hoped that this research will help inform the best way forward for a proof-of-concept demonstrator for such a morphing structure.

2 METHOD

The same model as is described in Dionisi et al. [9] is used here. A brief summary of the method is described below.

The method is based on CLPT, and to overcome the fact that the stresses near the free edges of the plate become three-dimensional an amalgamation of different approximation methods was devised for

shear and transverse interlaminar stresses. The methods amalgamated were Kassapoglou & Lagace [10] (symmetric laminates under uniaxial loading); Lin, Hsu & Ko [11] (extended previous method for unsymmetric laminates); Morton and Webber [12] (extended original method for thermal loading); and Stiftinger [13] (generalised original method for unsymmetric laminates with thermal loading).

The carbon fibre expansions caused by intercalation of Li are modelled as analogous to thermal expansions, with an intercalation coefficient being devised in place of a coefficient of thermal expansion. The intercalation coefficient α is calculated in the longitudinal direction (subscript L, along the fibre) and the corresponding expansion is given by equation 1 taken from Dionisi et al. [9]:

$$\varepsilon_L = \alpha_L C \quad (1)$$

where C represents the capacity (in mAh/g) of the carbon fibre (analogous to the temperature in a thermal problem). Input data for the expansion and capacity of the carbon fibres is taken from experimental data in Jacques et al. [7] and is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Electrochemical expansion properties for carbon fibre layer of actuation device (data from Dionisi et al., [9]).

	α_L (g/mAh)	C (mAh/g)	ε_L
CF Layer	1.58e-5	108	0.0017

For this analysis a single celled actuation device is modelled, consisting of three layers – two of Toray T800H carbon fibre, and a separator layer made from an isotropic glass fibre chopped strand mat. All three layers are modelled as being embedded in an SBE matrix, data for which was taken from Johannisson et al. [14]. A summary of the mechanical properties for these materials can be found in Table 2. The dimensions of the modelled device were chosen so as to be feasible for a first experimental demonstrator, these dimensions are Length: 50mm, Width: 10mm, Thickness: 0.6mm. This gives a mass of $m_{cf}=0.278g$ for the two carbon fibre layers. The models assume that one end of the laminate is built-in, forming a cantilever.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the actuation device layers, taken from Dionisi et al. [9] and Johannisson et al. [14].

	t (mm)	V_f	E_L (MPa)	E_T (MPa)	G_{LT} (MPa)	ν_{LT}	ν_{T3}
CF Layers	0.25	0.5	175200	5386	2702	0.3	0.3
GF Layer	0.1	0.5	13500	13500	3945	0.25	0.25
SBE Matrix	-	-	750	750	-	-	-

In order to validate the analytical model an FE model was programmed in Abaqus consisting of laminated composite shell elements (S4R). Appropriate thermal expansion coefficients were then

assigned to each layer and an appropriate thermal step was added to simulate the intercalation expansion for the capacity given in Table 1.

An analytical calculation of the tip deflections was used to estimate the range in which the CLPT solution would be valid. It was found that the linear solution matched the non-linear solution for tip displacements of up to 30mm for the given actuator geometry.

An analytical prediction of the likelihood of delamination for the two layups was also carried out. This was based on the Quadratic Delamination Criterion described in Dionisi et al. [9], taken from Brewer & Lagace [15] and reproduced in equation 2 below:

$$f_{risk} = \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{13}}{Z_{13}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{23}}{Z_{23}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{33}}{Z_{33}}\right)^2 < 1 \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$ is the average interlaminar stress calculated using the method of Kim & Soni [16], Z_{ij} is the estimated interlaminar strengths, and f_{risk} is the delamination risk coefficient. Values of f_{risk} greater than 1 indicate a risk for delamination. Values for Z_{ij} were estimated as the following: $Z_{13}=33\text{MPa}$, $Z_{23}=33\text{MPa}$, and $Z_{33}=17\text{MPa}$, based on a comparison of mechanical properties of the SBE with more conventional matrix systems.

Two test cases were analysed, corresponding to two layups of the laminated structure forming the actuator. The first, which results in a bending motion, has the layup $[0^\circ, 0^\circ_{sep}, 0]^\circ$. The second, which results in a bending/twisting motion, has the layup $[0^\circ, 0^\circ_{sep}, 30^\circ]$. It should be noted that the separator material is considered to be isotropic, and so its layup direction does not affect the resulting mode of the actuator deformation.

Both test cases were run using a capacity determined by the maximum displacement for which the linear solution was deemed to give satisfactory results. For the bend and bend/twist cases this corresponded to a capacity of 110 mAh/g.

An analysis of the interlaminar stresses is given for multiple layups, as well as a discussion about whether it is likely that such deformations could cause delamination based on the failure criteria discussed in Dionisi et al. [9].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two layups corresponding to two different modes of bending were modelled: a bending layup $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ]$ and a bend/twist layup $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 30^\circ]$. These were modelled both analytically and using an FE model. The results for the two cases are presented below.

Figure 2: Bending actuator with layup $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ]$ modelled (A) using an analytical model, and (B) using an FE model

Figure 2 shows the results for the bending actuator layup, and corresponds to a reversible intercalation capacity of 108 mAh/g. Figure 2A shows the analytical model, while Figure 2B shows the FE model. It can be seen that a relatively low capacity results in an appreciable deformation of the laminate in pure bending. The results from both the analytical and FE models agree with each other with the former giving a maximum tip displacement of 24 mm, while the latter gives a maximum tip displacement of approximately 22 mm. The discrepancy between the two is thought to be caused by the fact that the analytical model is only suitable for small deformations, and likely overpredicts deflections close to the boundary of this range. Based on data from Jacques et al. [7] the capacity modelled here can be obtained with a current density of 100mA/g, giving a time to maximum deflection of approximately 18 minutes. Slower charge rates would result in higher capacities, and hence larger deflections but would take longer to achieve.

Figure 3: Bend/twist actuator with layup $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 30^\circ]$ modelled (A) using an analytical model, and (B) using an FE model

Figure 3 shows the results for the bend/twist actuator layout, and corresponds to a reversible intercalation capacity of 108 mAh/g. Figure 3A shows the analytical model, while Figure 3B shows the FE model. It can be seen that a relatively low capacity results in an appreciable deformation of the laminate in a mixture of bending and twisting. The results from both the analytical and FE models agree with each other with the former giving a maximum tip displacement of 12 mm, while the latter gives a maximum tip displacement of approximately 13 mm.

It is interesting to note that, despite a seemingly low expansion along the fibre direction of the carbon fibres caused by Li-ion intercalation ($\approx 0.17\%$ for a capacity of 108 mAh/g), it is theoretically possible to create relatively large deformations at a laminate level. It should be noted here that layer thicknesses of the carbon fibre layers, $t_f=0.25\text{mm}$, and the separator layer, $t_s=0.1\text{mm}$ have been used. It is expected that these layer thicknesses could be reduced significantly in reality which would result in even larger deformations.

Figure 4: Estimated likelihood of delamination calculated using the Quadratic Delamination Criterion from Dionisi et al. [9] for different combinations of layer orientations.

One of the obvious concerns with such an actuation device is that internal stress from the expansions could cause damage to the structure itself. For this reason an analysis of the likelihood of delamination was carried out using the Quadratic Delamination Criterion described above, with estimated interlaminar strengths $Z_{13}=33\text{MPa}$, $Z_{23}=33\text{MPa}$, and $Z_{33}=17\text{MPa}$. Both layers of carbon fibre were swept through orientations of 0-90° and values of f_{risk} were calculated for each combination. Values of $f_{\text{risk}} > 1$ indicate a risk for delamination. Results from this analysis can be seen in Figure 4. It can be seen clearly that all combinations of layer orientations result in values of f_{risk} well below 1, with the maximum value of 0.125 occurring for the layups $[45^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ]$ and $[45^\circ, 0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. This indicates that there is no layup for which the actuation deformations examined here are likely to result in delamination. It should be noted however that these values are very dependent on the values estimated for the interlaminar strengths, which would ideally be obtained more accurately through experimental analysis.

These results show that it is indeed feasible to create a morphing laminate from carbon fibre plies actuated by lithium intercalation. It should be noted that the simplified laminate design here does not include any provision for current collectors which would be needed in order to apply current to the two carbon fibre layers. In structural battery research the most common current collector material to connect

carbon fibre to a source of current is copper, which would add a small amount to the mass of the device. There is also no consideration here for any kind of barrier layer to encapsulate the 3-layer device. This would be necessary in order to prevent the evaporation of electrolyte from the SBE, and would most likely add marginally to the stiffness of the layup.

4 CONCLUSIONS

From this analysis it can be seen that the concept of a laminated carbon fibre composite actuator based on ion intercalation is feasible. Relatively large deflections could be achieved, albeit at relatively low frequencies (in the range of mHz). The deformation shape can be tailored by altering the fibre directions therefore producing combinations of bending and twisting deformations. An analysis of the likelihood of delamination occurring showed that there are no layups for which delamination is likely based on the estimated interlaminar strengths, and it is therefore unlikely that such a device would suffer from delamination in normal operational conditions. If such a device could be realised it could fulfil the need for low-density solid-state actuation materials in industries such as aerospace and renewables. It is hoped that this work will help inform the future design and testing of demonstrator-sized laminated carbon fibre composite actuators.

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